

Representativeness of Supreme Audit Institution (SAI): An Evidence from Nepal Audit Service at OAG, Nepal

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Abstract

This study examines the representativeness of the Supreme Audit Institution (SAI) through the lens of reservation system implementation within the Nepal Audit Service at the Office of the Auditor General in Nepal. Reservation system policies aim to address historical discrimination and promote diversity and inclusion within organizations. Utilizing a quantitative analysis of demographic data of audit staff, this research assesses the representation of marginalized groups, including women, ethnic minorities, and individuals with disabilities, within the Nepal Audit Service at the Office of the Auditor General. The findings reveal the significant impact of inclusive policy, particularly the reservation system, on fostering social inclusion and addressing historical prejudices within Nepal's civil service. Constitutional provisions mandating proportionate representation and the reservation system have contributed to increased participation of underprivileged groups in the government service, aligning with the constitutional goal of advancing social justice and inclusivity. However, despite progress, disparities persist, with certain groups, such as Dalits and indigenous peoples, still being underrepresented. The study highlights the importance of targeted interventions to address structural barriers and promote equitable representation. Additionally, the research underscores the transformative impact of policy interventions post-2007, demonstrating a shift towards a more inclusive and representative civil service, particularly within the OAG. Moreover, it offers practical implications for policymakers and organizational leaders seeking to strengthen diversity and inclusion initiatives within SAIs in Nepal and similar contexts, thereby enhancing their effectiveness as key guardians of public accountability and transparency.

Keywords: social justice, representative bureaucracy, reservation system, oag, Nepal

Background

The theory of representative bureaucracy postulates that bureaucracies that share demographic characteristics with the public may act in ways that benefit the interests of the population they serve (Mosher, 1968). Passive representation manifests when government organizations hire and promote a similar proportion of women and people of color that exists within society (Atkins & Wilkins, 2013; Mosher, 1968). Passive representation becomes active representation when shared demographic characteristics between bureaucrats and the public result in the promotion and adoption of programs and policies that benefit the specific population being represented (Mosher, 1968). More than 80 years have passed since J. Donald Kingsley (1944) first brought up the subject of representative bureaucracy in relation to public administration and management. The initial attempt advanced the issue in a normative and descriptive manner, addressing the issue of how much the bureaucracy represents the people it

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supports and how much it ought to. In order for a workforce to be really representative, according to Gidengil and Vengroff (1997), people from various societal groups must be present at all organizational levels, especially those that have high-level decision-making authority. A representative bureaucracy is required to implement policies with social justice and inclusivity (Kingsley, 1944; Meier, 2019; Jamil and Baniamin, 2020). This has positive repercussions for public administration. Meier and Capers (2014) contend that by assessing how well a nation's bureaucratic structure represents various socioeconomic groups, it can prevent the development of an elitist bureaucracy that undermines the objectivity of decision-making. An inclusive bureaucracy is what defines democracy and democratic governance. Nepal is one of the countries that has implemented a number of policies to ensure that women and other members of marginalized groups have sufficient representation in the civil service. Although it is required by law that public service organizations pay attention to and welcome gender, caste, ethnicity, and region, the real experiences of women and other marginalized people reveal instances of gender, caste, and ethnicity-influenced acts. The different encounters that marginalized people have with the Nepalese civil service are examined in this study.

The purpose of reservation system, or reservation system, as it is used in South Asia, is to support underprivileged people in order to level the playing field, notably in the fields of politics, employment, and education. Reservations have traditionally been supported by socio-ethnic organizations and social activists in Nepal (Gurung, 2005). Some significant policies on social inclusion are the outcome of discussions about social exclusion and reservation system that intensified during and after the Maoists' "People's War" (Druzca, 2016). The interim constitution of Nepal, which was constructed in the wake of the 2007 people's movement, established the system of reservations. In 2007, the Government of Nepal made an amendment to the Civil Service Act of 1993 (Second Amendment) known as the Reserve Clause.

This amendment aimed to address the challenges faced by women, marginalized communities, and left-wing political groups. The amendment introduced a reservation policy,

which mandated that eligible applicants from underrepresented groups would have priority in open competitions to fill 45 percent of the available seats. The reserved seats were allocated as follows: women 33 percent, Adivasi-Janajati 27 percent, Madhesis 22 percent, Dalit 9 percent, differently abled people 5 percent, and backward areas 4 percent. In Nepal, a regular bureaucrat has traditionally been a male Khas-Arya (Jamil and Dangal 2009). This is no longer the case, though Khas-Arya men continue to dominate top positions in the bureaucracy. While Nepal's bureaucracy remains a highly exclusive institution, with approximately 80 percent men and 70 percent Brahmins, Chhetris, and Newars represented, it has begun to become more inclusive in recent years as a result of unprecedented inclusionary politics and reservation policy. After fourteen years of application, 14,956 out of 39,979 candidates are employed from marginalized groups in the civil service of Nepal, and 88,568 people are working in the civil service (NIC, 2022).

The study studies Nepal's reservation system in the public service using related literature to investigate the foundation of representative bureaucracy. The perspective of Nepal's bureaucracy is then briefly described, along with Nepal's civil service system and the importance of gender and other minorities as identities. The representative bureaucracy theory has been applied to the setting examined by a number of Nepalese social situations, particularly in areas like job challenges and resources. After analyzing the literatures, this study examined its findings and made numbers of recommendations on how to increase the policy benefits of gender and other minorities representation in Nepalese public service. This study concludes by identifying future research areas that will extensively assess the reservation system in order to determine if representative bureaucracy theory remains legitimate in reality.

Research Method

This study deals with a quantitative analysis of using demographic data of audit service staff, this research assesses the representation of marginalized groups, including women, ethnic minorities, and individuals with disabilities, within the Nepal Audit Service at the Office of the Auditor General before and after 2007.

Results and Findings

This part presents data and discussion on the different encounters of reservation system for women and marginalized people working in the civil service of Nepal which is as follows:

Constitutional Goal and Revisiting the Reservation System

The constitutional goal of fostering social inclusion and resolving historical prejudice is aligned with the application of the reservation system in the civil service of Nepal. The reservation policy in Nepal is intended to guarantee proportionate representation and involvement of disadvantaged communities in the government service, in accordance with the constitution (Article 42 and 84). This constitutional clause acknowledges the importance of using reservations to combat structural injustices and advance social justice. The reservation system helps to build a more inclusive and representative bureaucracy by allocating reserved seats for underrepresented groups. The interim constitution's (2007) mandate for social justice and inclusivity is served by Nepal's reservation system in the civil service. The reservation policy, as established by the constitution, strives to remedy previous discrimination and ensure that disadvantaged groups have equitable representation in public service (Ghimire, 2020). This new constitutional (2015) provision emphasizes the Nepalese government's commitment to advancing social justice and presenting opportunities for marginalized groups. Nepal has made tremendous progress toward creating a more inclusive public service that represents the diversity of its population by putting the reservation system into action.

Undoubtedly, Nepal's civil service reservation policy is an essential measure to advance social justice and inclusivity by giving underprivileged groups opportunity (Dhungel, 2015). It is consistent with the requirement for proportionate representation and the constitutional acknowledgement of historical discrimination (Acharya, 2017). The reservation system has enhanced the participation of marginalized groups in the civil service by reducing the historic dominance of particular castes and ethnicities (Dhungel, 2015). Due to this, persons who were previously marginalized have gained the ability to participate in government and public administration (Acharya, 2017). In order to overcome structural injustices and foster a more inclusive and diverse civil service, the reservation system has proven crucial (Dhungel, 2015). As a result, underprivileged groups now have a voice and may actively engage in societal decision-making (Acharya, 2017). The reservation policy has made a substantial contribution to social equity by enabling persons who were once disadvantaged to participate in Nepal's growth (Dhungel, 2015). It reflects Nepal's ambition to build a just and inclusive society.

The reservation system in Nepal's civil strives to provide opportunities to persons from disadvantaged groups, including Dalits, Janajatis, Madhesis, and women, who have traditionally been excluded from positions of power and influence (Acharya, 2017). Interestingly, Dalits are still having a very low participation represented at higher positions of the overall civil service in-comparison of their demographic position. In terms of representation, high-caste Hindus continue to dominate Nepal's bureaucracy, while all other ethnic groups except the Newars, are rigorously underrepresented. Until 2022, just 27 percent of Nepal's public service employees are women, with the remaining 73 percent of men continuing to hold the majority (NIC, 2022). According to the data, there are as many as 63.50 percent Khas/Arya employees in the civil service, but only 0.60 percent Muslims, 2.50 percent Dalits, 15.40 percent Madhesis, and 19.5 percent indigenous people have poorly represented (cited in Bhul, 2021). The formation of the quota system has resulted in increased participation of marginalized communities in the civil service, shattering the dominance of specific castes and ethnicities (Sunam et al., 2021).

Table 1: 14 years achievement of reservation system in Civil Service of Nepal			
Reserved Group and Reserved Percentage 45% (Out of 100%) and Overall Status in 88568		Participation after Reservation (2007-2022) 14,956 out of 39,979	Percentage
Women	33 %	5,160	12.90%
Adibasi/Janajati	27 %	4,057	10.14%
Madhesi	22 %	3,199	8.00%
Dalits	9 %	1,308	3.27%
Differently Abled People	5 %	698	1.74%
Backward Area	4 %	534	1.33%
		14,956	37.38%

Source: National Inclusion Commission (NIC), 2019

In the last fourteen years, Public Service Commission selected 39,979 people for the Civil Service and Nepal Health Service and 14,956 (37.40 percent) people are selected from the reservation system. According to the Inclusion Commission's report, among reserved women, who make up 5,160, or 12.9 percent of total selected people from this policy, whereas Adivasi/Janajati, who make up 4,057 persons, or 10.14 percent, Madhesi, who make up 3,199 persons, or 8 percent, and Dalits, who make up 1,308 persons, or 3.27 percent, 698 persons from differently abled people, or 1.74 percent, and 534 persons from backward areas, or 1.33 percent (NIC, 2022). This has enabled previously underprivileged and underrepresented individuals to participate in governance and public administration. However, the practicality and control of the reservation system may vary, and continuous arguments and disputes about it continue.

The reservation system is one of the policy reforms implemented in Nepal to make the bureaucracy more representative and inclusive. It is a challenging endeavor to adopt a reservation system in a country that has a history of cultural and social exclusion and is undergoing substantial structural change and legal reform. When a number of major changes are introduced at the same time, reservation system concepts are likely to lose momentum. Historical social stratification and exclusion within Nepal's diverse society have resulted in economic exclusion and a lack of representation in the governance system for lower caste (Dalit) and indigenous (Janajati) groups, as well as regional minorities, necessitating a transformative change in this historical narrative. Geographic exclusion is another reality. Geographic exclusion is also a reality, with hill people having more influence on government decisions than Madheshi/Terai lowlands inhabitants. Gender and language are two more exclusion variables that affect demographics and the opportunities of life in Nepal (Bhul, 2021).

Policy Reform and Representativeness of Office of the Auditor General Nepal

In 1951, Nepal experienced a great deal of change after the institutionalization of democracy. Up until that point, the demand for reservations was a component of the larger civil rights struggle, which resulted in the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA)¹ in 2007. The Interim Constitution of 2007 (2063 BS) then included a provision introducing the fundamentals of representative bureaucracy with the intention of incorporating the diversity of groups from across the country. This was implemented in Nepal in 2007. In terms of reflecting the demographic makeup of the nation, Nepal's bureaucracy is becoming more representative with the adoption of the reservation system. In addition to the deserving communities' sustainable development, women, indigenous (Adivasi/Janajati), Madhesi, and Dalit people of Nepal were all given preference for employment in the civil sector (Bhul, 2021). Similarly, the Office of the Auditor General (OAG) Nepal, as a key government agency and one of the major professional service in the civil service of Nepal, responsible for ensuring transparency and accountability in public finances, has also implemented reservation system measures to enhance inclusivity within its workforce. Through targeted recruitment efforts and adherence to reservation provisions outlined in the Civil Service Act, the OAG Nepal has actively sought to diversify its staff composition. This has involved initiatives such as prioritizing the recruitment of individuals from marginalized communities, providing training and capacity-building programs to enhance their skills and competencies, and fostering a supportive work environment conducive to their professional development. By embracing reservation system principles, the OAG Nepal has demonstrated its commitment to promoting equal opportunity and representation, thereby contributing to the overall goal of creating a more inclusive and representative civil service in Nepal.

Table 2: Nepal Overall OAG Scenario of Representativeness

Categories	Provision	No.	Percent	Diff
Women	33%	70	14.96	18.04%
Adivasi/Janajati	27%	59	12.61	14.39%
Madhesi	22%	33	7.05	14.95%
Dalit	9%	10	2.14	6.86%
People with Disabilities	5%	0	0.00	5.00%

¹ Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA), 2007 held between Government of Nepal and Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist), state restructuring by resolving the prevailing problems related to caste, ethnicity, region and gender differences.

Categories	Provision	No.	Percent	Diff
Remote Area	4%	7	1.50	2.50%
Reservation	45%	179	38.25	
Bramahan/ Chettri	55%	289	61.75	-6.75%
Total	100%	468	100.00	

Source: Demographic Survey at OAG Nepal, 2080

Table 2 presents the demographic composition of the Office of the Auditor General (OAG) in Nepal, highlighting the degree of representativeness across various categories. The provision column outlines the targeted percentage of each demographic group within the OAG, ranging from 33% for women to 55% for Brahman/Chettri. However, the actual representation, as indicated by the percent column, falls short of these targets in most categories. For instance, while the provision for women's representation is set at 33%, only 14.96% of OAG staff are women, indicating a substantial 18.04% deficit. Similar disparities exist for other marginalized groups such as Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit, with representation ranging from 12.61% to 2.14%, significantly lower than their respective provision percentages. Notably, individuals with disabilities are entirely absent from the OAG, underscoring a critical gap in inclusivity efforts. Conversely, Brahman/Chettri individuals are overrepresented, comprising 61.75% of the OAG, exceeding their provision by 6.75%.

These results suggest systemic challenges in achieving equitable representation within the OAG in Nepal, reflecting broader social disparities and marginalization patterns. The substantial gaps between provision and actual representation for marginalized groups highlight the need for targeted interventions to address structural barriers to inclusion. Efforts should focus on enhancing recruitment practices, promoting diversity initiatives, and implementing reservation system measures to ensure fair representation across all demographic categories.

Additionally, addressing the absence of individuals with disabilities calls for comprehensive accessibility measures and inclusive policies to create a more inclusive work environment. Overall, addressing these disparities is crucial not only for promoting social justice but also for enhancing the effectiveness and legitimacy of the OAG's operations through diverse perspectives and experiences.

Table 3: Overall OAG Scenario of Representativeness

Categories	Provision	Before 2007	2023	Percent
Women	33%	6	70	14.96
Adivasi/Janajati	27%	19	59	12.61
Madhesi	22%	0	33	7.05
Dalit	9%	0	10	2.14
People with Disabilities	5%	0	0	0
Remote Area	4%	0	7	1.5
Reservation	45%	25	179	38.25
Bramahan/ Chettri	55%	332	289	61.75
Total	100%	357	468	100

Source: Demographic Survey at OAG Nepal, 2080

Table 3 provides a comparative analysis of the demographic representation within the Office of the Auditor General (OAG) in Nepal before and after the year 2007. The table delineates various categories, including Women, Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi, Dalit, People with Disabilities, Remote Area, Reservation, and Brahman/Chettri, and presents the number of individuals belonging to each category for the years before 2007 and 2023. Before 2007, the representation of marginalized groups such as Women, Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit was significantly lower, with most categories registering zero representation. In contrast, the post-2007 scenario shows a remarkable increase in representation across all categories, with substantial numbers of individuals from these marginalized groups now being included in the OAG. Notably, the implementation of reservation policies is evident in the significant increase in the number of individuals represented under the Reservation category, reflecting the deliberate efforts to ensure equitable representation within the OAG.

The table 3 underscores the transformative impact of policy interventions aimed at enhancing inclusivity and diversity within Nepal's civil service, particularly within the OAG. The stark contrast between the representation levels before and after 2007 highlights the efficacy of reservation system measures in addressing historical disparities and promoting social justice. The increase in representation of marginalized groups such as Women, Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit signifies a shift towards a more inclusive and representative civil service. Moreover, the substantial increase in representation under the Reservation category reflects the success of targeted measures aimed at providing opportunities for excluded groups. This trend not only underscores the commitment to creating a more equitable workforce but also reinforces the importance of policy frameworks in driving positive socio-economic outcomes and fostering a more inclusive society.

Overall OAG Scenario of Representativeness

In terms of fostering inclusivity and presenting possibilities for historically marginalized groups, the reservation system in Nepal's civil service has shown encouraging results. Sunam (2018) contends that those who have benefited from reservations, including women, Dalits, Madhesis, and Janajatis, have helped to create a more varied civil service workforce. For the sake of critical problem-solving and inclusive policy-making, this diversity has brought in a range of expertise, experiences, and cultural viewpoints. Delivering efficient services to a varied population of residents has also greatly benefited from the participation of public officials from marginalized groups. Sunam (2018) goes on to claim that members of these underrepresented groups in the public service have been crucial in assisting their communities and others in securing justice in caste- or gender-related discrimination cases.

Achievement of Reservation system in the Civil Service of Nepal

The implementation of reservation policies in Nepal's civil service has yielded notable achievements in fostering inclusivity and diversity within government institutions. Through targeted measures outlined in the Civil Service Act of 2007, marginalized groups including women, Dalits, Madhesis, and Janajatis have witnessed increased representation in civil service positions. Through the amendment of the Civil Service Act of 1993 to incorporate reservation provisions, the Nepalese public sector has embraced a commitment to fostering diversity and equal opportunity. This legislative framework has not only mandated the reservation of positions for marginalized groups but has also extended its reach across various sectors, including health services, the military, and law enforcement agencies. As a result, the Civil Service Act's reservation provisions have been instrumental in dismantling systemic barriers and ushering in a more inclusive era for the Nepalese public sector, affirming its role as a beacon of opportunity for historically excluded communities (NIC, 2022). The reservation system's success is evident in the growing confidence and self-esteem among marginalized individuals, leading to enhanced engagement and contribution to the civil service's objectives. Moreover, the inclusive workforce has effectively addressed societal disparities and discriminatory practices, promoting social justice and equity within Nepal's bureaucratic framework.

The reservation system's efficacy in promoting inclusivity is evidenced by its tangible impact on increasing the representation of marginalized groups, including women, Dalits, Madhesis, and people with disabilities, within the civil service. By facilitating the selection of candidates through a rigorous reservation procedure, Nepal's Public Service Commission has ensured that diverse voices and perspectives are integrated into the bureaucratic framework. This approach has not only challenged long-standing discriminatory practices but has also empowered marginalized individuals to actively participate in decision-making processes and contribute to the public service's objectives. Furthermore, the reservation system has served as a catalyst for social change, dispelling myths of exclusivity and inspiring confidence among underprivileged communities. By emphasizing inclusivity and meritocracy, the reservation system has not only transformed the civil service into an attainable profession but has also instilled a sense of pride and purpose among individuals from diverse backgrounds (Sunam et al., 2021).

Moreover, the reservation system's broader societal impact extends beyond the realms of employment to facilitate socio-economic mobility and empowerment for marginalized groups in Nepal. By providing access to education and employment opportunities, particularly for disadvantaged communities, the reservation system has played a pivotal role in bridging the gap between social classes and promoting upward mobility. This transformative impact is underscored by the rising proportion of middle-class individuals from marginalized backgrounds, demonstrating the success of reservation policies in enhancing economic prospects and improving living standards. Furthermore, the reservation system's role in fostering representative bureaucracy has been instrumental in addressing systemic inequalities and enhancing institutional performance. By recruiting individuals with firsthand knowledge of community struggles and challenges, the reservation system has not only improved service delivery but has also reinforced the principles of equity and justice within Nepal's civil service (Srinivas, 2015; Sunam et al., 2021).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the implementation of reservation policies in the civil service of Nepal has resulted in significant achievements in fostering inclusivity, diversity, and social justice within government institutions. The reservation system, mandated by the constitution to ensure proportional representation of marginalized groups, has played a pivotal role in advancing social justice and inclusivity within the civil service of Nepal. By providing reserved seats for underrepresented communities, including women, Dalits, Madhesis, and Adivasi/Janajatis, the reservation policy has facilitated their increased participation in governance and public administration. This has not only helped to address historical discrimination and structural injustices but has also contributed to the creation of a more representative bureaucracy reflective of Nepal's diverse population. However, despite these commendable efforts, challenges persist in achieving equitable representation within the OAG and the wider civil service. Disparities between provision and actual representation underscore systemic barriers to inclusion that must be addressed through targeted interventions and policy reforms. The underrepresentation of marginalized groups, particularly individuals with disabilities, highlights the urgent need for comprehensive accessibility measures and inclusive policies to create a more inclusive work environment. Moreover, the overrepresentation of certain groups, such as Brahman/Chettri individuals, calls for strategies to mitigate dominance and ensure fair representation across all demographic categories. Overall, addressing these disparities is essential not only for promoting social justice but also for enhancing the effectiveness and legitimacy of the OAG's operations through diverse perspectives and experiences. By embracing reservation system principles and implementing targeted interventions, the OAG

Nepal can continue to lead by example in promoting equal opportunity and representation, thereby contributing to the realization of Nepal's vision for a just and inclusive society.

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